

Characterization of FOWLP Process using Temporary Bonding Materials on Carrier with Very Low Die Shift

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Abstract — This study aims to link several epoxy mold compound (EMC) material properties to warpage and die-shift that are typically present in a fanout wafer level packaging process flow with RDL last process conditions. Two EMC compounds with different CTE, T_g , and modulus are evaluated and compared for warpage and die-shift performance on a next generation temporary bonding material (TBM). A low CTE and high T_g seem to be very beneficial to achieve low warpage on blanket mold on TBM wafers. When dies are embedded, the modulus plays a major role in order to mitigate thermal stresses that occur due to the Si-mold CTE mismatch during molding.

Keywords—epoxy mold compound, FOWLP, warpage, die-shift

I. INTRODUCTION

Fan-Out Wafer-Level Packaging (FOWLP) [1,2] represents a significant advancement in semiconductor packaging technology. It addresses the increasing demand for smaller form factors, higher I/O density, and enhanced performance in modern electronic devices. Unlike traditional packaging methods, FOWLP allows for the redistribution of electrical connections from the die to a larger area, which improves space utilization and electrical performance. This technology is particularly advantageous for applications requiring high-density interconnects such as mobile devices, high-performance computing, and automotive electronics. The process flow of FOWLP typically involves wafer dicing, die placement on a carrier, molding, redistribution layer (RDL) formation, and subsequent reconstitution and singulation.

One of the critical steps in FOWLP is the molding process, which involves encapsulating the individual dies with an epoxy molding compound (EMC). The primary purpose of molding is

to protect the dies from environmental damage, provide mechanical support, and ensure the structural integrity of the package. However, achieving uniform and defect-free molding is challenging due to several factors, including die-shift and warpage. [1-4] During the molding process, the dies are placed on a carrier substrate, and the EMC is applied to encapsulate the dies. The quality of molding significantly impacts the subsequent processes and the overall reliability of the final package. Factors such as mold material properties, mold temperature, and pressure play crucial roles in determining the quality of the molded package [3-5].

Die-shift is a significant concern in FOWLP, as it directly impacts the yield and reliability of the packaged devices. Die-shift refers to the misalignment of dies during the molding process, which can lead to misalignment of the RDLs and subsequently affect the electrical performance of the package. Several factors contribute to die-shift, including the properties of the die-attach film (DAF), die-attach pitch, and the mechanical properties of the EMC. During the molding process, the differential thermal expansion between the dies and the EMC can cause die movement. This movement results in misalignment issues that must be addressed to ensure the

TABLE I. EMC PROPERTIES

EMC	Material properties		
	T_g (°C)	CTE1/2	Modulus (MPa)
EMC-A	High	Low/ Medium	High
EMC-B	Low	Low/ High	Low

Fig. 1 Basic process flow (with or without die-placement step) of this study. A TBM is coated on the silicon wafer, followed by die-placement, over molding, grinding and a thermal cycle at 240°C for 1 hour. Warpage is measured after coating, post mold cure and grinding. Die-shift is measured after die-placement and post mold cure.

functionality of the final package. To mitigate die-shift, precise control of the die-attach process is essential. This includes accurate positioning of the dies on the carrier wafer and careful selection of molding parameters, such as temperature and pressure. Additionally, advanced materials and process control techniques can help reduce the occurrence of die-shift. For example, the use of low-stress EMCs and optimized die-attach adhesives can minimize the thermal mismatch and reduce die movement. In this study, two EMC compounds, with different material properties, will be evaluated for their compatibility with the next generation temporary bonding material (TBM), BrewerBOND® C1301-50 material. A blanket study is performed to evaluate the warpage of the system as a function of EMC thickness and its subsequent debonding performance. After this initial evaluation, dies of different thicknesses are placed on the TBM and over molded, after which the dies are revealed via grinding. Both the warpage of the system as well as potential die-shift are evaluated after molding, post mold cure, thinning and thermal cycling at 240°C to simulate an RDL-last process (Fig. 1). The properties of interest in this study are T_g , CTE1/2 and the modulus. As such two mold compounds were selected: EMC-A has a high T_g , low/medium CTE1/2 and high modulus, while EMC-B has a low T_g , low/high CTE1/2 and low modulus (Table I).

II. BASELINE MOLD PERFORMANCE

In a first step, both EMCs are evaluated for their baseline warpage, which is monitored during thinning and thermal process steps, after which their mechanical debonding compatibility with the TBM is evaluated.

A. Baseline warpage

The same flow as in Fig. 1 is followed without any die placement step. All the temporary bonding materials (TBMs) used in this study have the same thickness ($\sim 30 \mu\text{m}$). After

coating, the warpage of the coated wafers is measured as a control to verify that the TBM itself does not negatively affect the base line silicon wafer warpage. Several wafers are prepared with different thickness of EMC (200 μm & 585 μm) of each mold compound using the suppliers' recommended molding conditions. After the post mold cure step, the warpage was remeasured. The 200 μm thick mold compounds were thinned down to 50 μm and 100 μm , while the 585 μm mold compounds were thinned to 500 μm . Again a warpage measurement was performed. Finally the ground stack was subjected to a thermal cycle of 240°C for 1 hour to simulate an RDL cure step. The results are summarized in Table II and Fig. 2).

The warpage of the silicon carriers with TBM is very stable at -36 μm for each wafer. EMC-A and B can be compared step-by-step. Starting with the mold induced warpage (post mold cure), it is evident that EMC-A is much less dependent on the mold thickness compared to EMC-B (Fig. 2A). Whereas the warpage of compound A stays well below 200 μm even for mold thicknesses up to 585 μm , compound B is already at -700 μm for 200 μm mold thickness and well over -1 mm for 585 μm mold thickness. This behaviour can be explained by the T_g and

TABLE II. WARPAGE DATA MOLD ON TBM

EMC	Warpage (μm)			
	TBM coating	PMC	Thinning to [X]	Thermal cycle
EMC-A 200 μm	-36	180	[X=50 μm] 40	-200
EMC-B 200 μm	-36	-700	[X=50 μm] -140	-190
EMC-A 200 μm	-36	180	[X=100 μm] 100	-160
EMC-B 200 μm	-36	-700	[X=100 μm] -190	-300
EMC-A 585 μm	-36	178	[X=500 μm] 503	-216
EMC-B 585 μm	-36	-1117	[X=500 μm] 579	-1240

Fig. 2 Warpage evaluation for the different EMCs as function of mold thickness (A), final thinning thickness (B), after thermal cycle at 240°C (C). The effect of moisture uptake on warpage is highlighted for the thick EMC compound (D).

the CTE1/2 of both compounds. Although both compounds have a similar CTE1, their CTE2 is very different. EMC-B has a much higher CTE2 compared to EMC-A. At the same time, the T_g of EMC-A is much higher compared to EMC-B. Due to the very high T_g of EMC-A, it can be cured at high temperature without risk of exceeding the T_g , and hence, CTE1 remains valid. For EMC-B, the T_g is rather low, and in order to fully cure it, we need to perform the PMC at temperatures near or equal to the T_g which means CTE2 is valid. The difference between CTE1 and 2 will result in a larger CTE mismatch with the carrier wafer system.

The thinning operation gives insight in the behaviour of the mold compounds as a function of thickness as well. However, during the grinding step (and subsequent cleaning step) water and moisture can be ad/absorbed by the EMC, which can have a profound effect on the warpage. In order to highlight this effect, the thick mold compounds of 585 μm are thinned down to 500 μm . Both mold compounds relax significantly when thinned down to 50 μm or 100 μm to sub-100 μm for EMC-A, down

Fig. 3 Debonded mold on tape frame: EMC-A (A) and EMC-B (B); carrier with TBM: EMC-A (C) and EMC-B (D)

from around 200 μm , and sub -220 μm for EMC-B, an impressive decrease from -700 μm (Table II, Fig. 2B). Thinning down from 585 μm to 500 μm gives a major jump in the warpage from 178 μm up to 500 μm for EMC-A and a jump from -1117 μm to +579 μm for EMC-B. Such a large jump does not line up with the expected warpage reduction during thinning. Both mold compounds are heavily affected by moisture uptake during the grinding and subsequent cleaning steps. This is verified by performing a thermal cycle at 240°C for 1 hour (Table I, Fig. 2C). The warpage of EMC-A relaxes to sub -200 μm for all different mold thickness (even at 500 μm), while EMC-B reverts back to its original warpage around -1200 μm . The effect of moisture uptake is highlighted in Fig. 2D, where the results of the 585-500 μm mold compounds are summarized.

B. Debonding performance

Finally, all the mold compounds are flipped onto tape-frame, after which a mechanical debonding is performed. Both the debonded carrier as well as the debonded mold (on tape frame) is evaluated for residues (Fig. 3). Both mold compounds showed a stable and easy debonding; however, after inspection mold compound A had a ‘clean’ debonding, meaning no TBM residues could be detected on the debonded mold-on-tape frame. Compound B clearly had some TBM residues on the mold, indicating that the adhesion of compound B with respect to the TBM is higher than the adhesion between compound A and the respective mold compound.

So far, the mold compounds and their associated warpage as a function of thickness, thinning and thermal cycle as well as their debonding performance in combination with the TBM have been evaluated. Based on the results, it can be concluded that EMC-A is a good candidate for a wide range of EMC thicknesses as it is clear that after a thermal cycle the warpage for all investigated cases remains below 200 μm and the debonding from the TBM was neat. EMC-B on the other hand seems to be a good candidate if the mold thickness is limited.

III. EMBEDDED DIES

In this section the mold compounds are stress tested in the presence of Si dies. The evaluation is split into three parts; part A) a similar warpage study as for the blanket wafers, part B) a die-shift study and finally C) debonding in the presence of dies. For this part, dies of 50 μm and 100 μm were chosen, and as such, we limit the initial mold thickness to 200 μm . This will avoid unnecessary issues of handling the large warped wafers of 500 μm as observed for EMC-B.

A. Warpage in function of embedded dies.

The presence of silicon dies can increase warpage in a mold compound due to differences in the coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) between the silicon dies and the mold compound. When the assembly undergoes temperature changes during manufacturing or operation, these materials expand and contract at different rates, causing mechanical stresses. This mismatch can lead to uneven stress points, resulting in warpage

Fig. 4 Warpage evolution of both mold compounds with 50µm thick dies (A) and with 100µm thick dies (B).

or deformation of the mold compound. In order to evaluate this, wafers were again coated with the TBM layer after which the warpage was measured as a control. The warpage of all coated wafers was again very similar to around -36 µm. Next, several wafers were populated with either 50 µm thick dies or 100 µm thick dies. Each wafer had a population density of 25%. The die alignment with respect to the carrier wafer was measured (discussed in next section), and all die-populated wafers were over molded to a total mold thickness of 200 µm. After the PMC, the wafers were ground to reveal the dies (i.e. to 50 or 100 µm), and finally a thermal cycle of 240°C for 1 hour was performed. After each step the warpage was measured. Before the thermal cycle, the die-shift was measured again.

Table III summarizes the warpage results for the mold embedded die populated wafers. For this section, since we only have two types of dies, the results will be discussed per die thickness. For the 50 µm thick dies (Table III, Fig. 4A), the warpage after PMC is around -100 µm for EMC-A. It is worth noting that for the 200 µm mold compound without dies, the warpage was around 180 µm. This already suggests an interplay between Si dies and EMC. After grinding to reveal the dies, the warpage flips from -100 µm to 117 µm, but just as in the die-less case, seems to relax back to the post-grind case after the thermal anneal cycle at 240°C. EMC-B has a warpage around -600 µm after PMC. After thinning to 50 µm, the warpage seem to have relaxed all the way down to -100µm where it remains even after thermal cycle. In all steps of this flow the warpage of EMC-B is lower in the presence of dies compared to the die-less case, but seem to follow a similar predictable trend.

For the 100 µm thick dies (Table III, Fig. 4B), EMC-A shows a huge warpage of around -700 µm, which is 7 times more than the 50 µm die case and almost 4 times more than the respective die-less case. After revealing the dies, the warpage

relaxed to around -200 µm, only to jump up again to around -600 µm after the thermal cycle. The latter jump confirms again the moisture uptake (during grind) and its effect on warpage for this mold compound. While for EMC-B, the warpage evolution is very comparable to the case of 50 µm dies. The initial warpage after PMC is around -600 µm, which relaxes significantly during die-reveal to less than -200 µm where it stays even after thermal cycle. The associated wafer-level warpage plots and line scans of this 100 µm die split are shown in Fig. 5.

The effect of the dies on the warpage per mold compound deserves more discussion. EMC-B with dies behaves very similar to the die-less case, and the thickness of the dies seems to follow a logical mold thickness induced warpage trend. Compared to the die-less case, the warpage decreases somewhat in the presence of dies. The same cannot be said for EMC-A. While there is hardly any warpage for 50 µm thick dies, there is a 6-7 fold increase for the 100 µm thick dies after PMC & thermal cycle. A possible explanation can be found again in the differences between the CTE's and the modulus of both mold compounds. For the die-less case, we established that mold compound A has less warpage due to the higher T_g /lower CTE combination. However, when Si dies are present, stress builds up due to the CTE mismatch between Si and mold compound. A low modulus allows the material to deform more easily under thermal stresses, which means it can better accommodate the stress induced by the mismatch in thermal expansion between components (like silicon dies and mold compounds). This reduces the internal stresses that cause warpage, ultimately leading to less mold warpage compared to materials with a high modulus, which are more likely to resist deformation and cause warping under similar conditions.

As a summary for this warpage study with and without dies we make the following observations for the used EMCs:

- The higher T_g and low CTE1/2 of EMC-A effectively reduces warpage for the die-less case.
- When Si dies are present, the high modulus of EMC-A prevents a relaxation of the stress build up due to the CTE mismatch between mold and Si, leading to significant warpage.
- Low CTE and modulus are key to obtain low warpage when dies are present.
- Warpage after thinning is heavily influenced by moisture uptake. A thermal cycle is required to reveal the 'real' warpage.

TABLE III. WARPAGE DATA FOR DIE-EMBEDDED EMC ON TBM

EMC thickness	Warpage (µm) after			
	TBM coating	PMC	Thinning to [X]	Thermal cycle
EMC-A 200 µm	-36	-100	[X=50 µm] 117	-100
EMC-B 200 µm	-36	-600	[50 µm] -100	-100
EMC-A 200 µm	-36	-700	[X=100 µm] -190	-600
EMC-B 200 µm	-36	-600	[100 µm] -180	-200

Fig. 5 Wafer level warpage plots & line scans for EMC-A and B with embedded 100 μm dies after PMC to 200 μm , grinding to 100 μm and thermal cycle of 240°C.

B. Die-shift.

We have established that EMC-A has an excellent warpage behaviour in the case of 50 μm thick dies, while for thicker dies (100 μm) it is better to use EMC-B. However, warpage is only one part of the overall performance equation, die-shift is another key criteria. The alignment of all the dies in this study have been measured before molding and after thinning. The die-carrier alignment results have been collected in box plots per mold compound and process condition (Fig. 6). After die-placement, all wafers have a similar die-to-carrier mis-alignment around less than $2 \pm 0.8 \mu\text{m}$ with a few outliers, which is within the specifications of the used die-placement tool and recipe. After thinning, two conditions stand out, 1) a high die-shift is observed for all the EMC-A compounds (both the 50 and the 100 μm case) up to around 80 μm on average with a very large spread, 2) For EMC-B (zoom in on Fig. 6B) there is no significant die-shift observed for the 50 μm thick die case and less than 1 μm shift for the 100 μm case. It needs to be noted that a very precise pre and post mold die-alignment measurement is not as straightforward as it seems, as the mold matrix and potential warpage can have an effect on the brightness, contrast, focus and in general the marker recognition, which can alter the actual measurement accuracy. Die-shift on thermoplastic types of materials is typically associated with the reflow of the TBM under the mold or PMC conditions [2]. However, the TBM used in this study is a thermoset material that is fully cured before die-stacking, so a reflow under the used conditions is not expected. Furthermore, a reflow of TBM would likely result in a die-shift for both mold compounds. It is possible that the larger stiffness (higher modulus) of EMC-A exerts more force on the dies

Fig. 6 A) Box plots of the die-to-carrier alignment after die-placement and after post mold cure for 50 and 100 μm thick dies embedded in EMC-A or EMC-B. B) Zoom in for EMC-B.

Fig. 7 Die-embedded (50 μm) mold compounds on tape frame. A) EMC-A and B) EMC-B.

during the mold process. However, considering the magnitude of the die-shift, it is very likely that there is a chemical interaction between the mold compound and the TBM. As the mold compound and TBM compositions are trademark secrets, it is not possible to comment on such a potential interaction.

C. Mold embedded die-debonding.

Finally, we verify whether the embedded dies negatively affect the debonding performance of the mold compound from the used TBM system. All systems could be easily mechanically debonded without issues. The same conclusion for the blanket mold compounds can be made. EMC-A has an extremely neat debond, while EMC-B has a few TBM residues transferred to the mold. It is worth noting that EMC-B looks very smooth on the tape-frame for both thicknesses, while EMC-A clearly shows wrinkles, which are more pronounced for the 50 μm dies than for the 100 μm dies. This again points out to stresses that have been built up within the mold around the dies that could not be compensated during the molding step or PMC due to the high mold modulus.

IV. CONCLUSION

A blanket mold study on TBM reveals that the EMC with low CTE, high T_g and high modulus has a superior warpage behaviour compared the EMC with a high CTE. The EMC with low T_g and low modulus including a very thick mold and simulated RDL cure at 240°C had much higher warpage. However, embedding dies into the mold compound changes the warpage behaviour completely. While it is reasonable to assume that the lower CTE and higher T_g would still be beneficial in the case of dies, likely the high modulus material has difficulties in accommodating for the stress induced by the CTE mismatch between Si and mold, while the lower modulus material will

more easily adjust to the generated thermal stresses. This study clearly shows that pure blanket mold evaluations alone are not sufficient to assess the warpage behaviour within a more real FOWLP application. Furthermore, die-shifts can vary drastically between two mold compounds even if the same TBM system is used.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J. Lau *et al.*, "Warpage and Thermal Characterization of Fan-Out Wafer-Level Packaging," 2017 IEEE 67th Electronic Components and Technology Conference (ECTC), Orlando, FL, USA, 2017, pp. 595-602, doi: 10.1109/ECTC.2017.309. J. Clerk Maxwell, A Treatise on Electricity and Magnetism, 3rd ed., vol. 2. Oxford: Clarendon, 1892, pp.68-73.
- [2] A. Podpod, D. Velenis, A. Phommahaxay, P. Bex, F. Fodor, E.J. Marinissen, K. Rebis, A. Miller, G. Beyer, E. Beyne, "High Density and High Bandwidth Chip-To-Chip Connections with 20 μm Pitch Flip-Chip on Fan-Out Wafer Level Package", 2018 International Wafer Level Packaging Conference (IWLPC), San Jose, CA, 2018, pp. 1-5.
- [3] Y. Oi, Y. Fujii, T. Hiraoka, Y. Yada and K. Kan, "Warpage Control of Liquid Molding Compound for Fan-Out Wafer Level Packaging," 2018 IEEE 68th Electronic Components and Technology Conference (ECTC), San Diego, CA, USA, 2018, pp. 967-972, doi: 10.1109/ECTC.2018.00148.
- [4] C. Xu, P. Sun, Z. Liu and J. Liu, "Wafer Compression Molding Warpage Optimization for Wafer Level Package," 2020 21st International Conference on Electronic Packaging Technology (ICEPT), Guangzhou, China, 2020, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ICEPT50128.2020.9202618.
- [5] A. Salahouelhadj, M. Gonzalez, A. Podpod, K. Rebis and E. Beyne, "Study of the influence of material properties and geometric parameters on warpage for Fan-Out Wafer Level Packaging," 2018 7th Electronic System-Integration Technology Conference (ESTC), Dresden, Germany, 2018, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ESTC.2018.8546433.